

Sustaining the Growth of the Islamic Financial Industry: What Needs to Be Done?

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Introduction

The latest global financial crisis, created within the conventional financial system, has brought the Islamic financial industry ("IFI") into the limelight as a possible and viable alternative. Many advocates of the Islamic economic system have started arguing that this is the chance for the IFI to take centre stage in the world economy. They consider the IFI as the light at the end of the tunnel. On the other hand, those more cautious and better-versed in the current status of the IFI are aware of the challenges. For them, the IFI is still too young to take centre stage or to replace the conventional economic system in the global economy. Although they believe that Islamic finance is the way forward, it is too early for this big step.

Being a niche industry, Islamic finance faces a long way ahead that needs to be conquered before it can be elevated to the next level (Singh, 2009). The conventional economy has a history of more than 300 years and is well developed, despite the shocks from the recent crisis. To expect the IFI to jump

over these 300 years of development is equal to suicide and far from reality.

However, some steps may be taken in order to foster and speed up the process of the IFI's development by focusing on, among others, the relevant focal points for sustaining the growth of the industry.

As one author stated, the IFI "is in its adolescence when it comes to issues like transparency, accounting and ratings, with very different standards being used" (Robinson). For the IFI to develop further and to establish its position within mainstream global finance, it needs to make vast improvements with regard to transparency as well as to improve its credibility through the harmonisation of standards and practices.

Islamic finance is far from perfect. To begin with, it is facing a number of ongoing challenges that need to be addressed head on. It is the way Muslim scholars will respond to these challenges that will determine the future of Islamic finance, as stated by Karuvelil (2000, pg 155) in the next statement:

“The [Islamic finance] industry faces considerable challenges; its response to them will determine whether it becomes a significant alternative to the conventional system in global financial markets.” Moreover, the lack of efficient legal framework, standards and procedures, qualified manpower, and effective government support increases the risk exposures of the Islamic financial industry (Khorshid, 2009).

Current Status of Islamic Financial Industry

Today, the Islamic finance industry is officially recognised within the global financial arena as an independent and entirely feasible financial system. The market and demand for Islamic finance exist; it is significant and poised for further growth and expansion. However, if Islamic finance is to reach its optimal potential, a critical priority now is to ensure that the industry is firmly entrenched within a sound operating framework that forms a solid foundation for future development. Building this foundation should be accomplished before the industry moves on to a new phase characterised by innovation and expansion of industry product offerings. But the rate of new product launches and the current dynamic state of Islamic finance suggests that the industry may well have moved on to this next phase before actually achieving that solid foundation. This is potentially problematic in the long run, when one considers the need to achieve a sustainable rate of growth in a rapidly evolving industry. (Ebrahim, 2004, pg 264)

The author of the citation above is right when he states that there are both market and demand for Islamic finance, which has grown into a USD1 trillion (RM3.5 trillion) industry, with prospects to grow even further in future. Moreover, there is growing awareness among the Muslim population about this industry looking for business activities that are in line with *Shari'ah* teachings. Furthermore, the author is also correct when he says that the IFI has rushed into the next phase without really solidifying its foundation; this may be detrimental to the future development of the IFI.

In my opinion, however, the IFI is not an independent system on its own. Many authors share this view, that the IFI is currently only a sub-set of the conventional financial system. It is also being argued that Islamic finance is converging towards the conventional system. According to Habib Ahmad, Islamic finance “is moving more and more closely to conventional finance” and it is “mimicking most of the products of conventional finance” (Brant, 2009; Smolo, 2007, pgs 30, 44-45, 135-136).

There is no doubt that the IFI needs a uniformity and standardisation as well as more regulatory, supervisory and transparency procedures that will improve its position within the global financial market. Uniformity and standardisation will promote a sound and stable Islamic financial system and make it a viable and credible component of the global financial system, while the supervisory and regulatory standards will bring about the credibility of Islamic finance (Ahmed, 2006, pg 439).

Some Unresolved Issues in Islamic Finance

i. Role of Human Capital in the Development of Islamic Finance

Many factors influence economic development in general, and the development of a financial sector in particular. Some of the factors range from social to cultural, from economic policies to institutional development. The question here is: What is the role of human capital in the development of the IFI?

Some argue that human capital is the main factor that determines the economic growth or decline of a particular country (Garavan, Morley, Gunnigle, & Collins, 2001). Consequently, human capital is considered as “the ultimate basis of the wealth of nations” (Hashi & Hareed).

The IFI has been growing rapidly over the years. However, this has not been followed by the development of enough human capital, as the industry faces a huge shortage of experienced *Shari'ah* scholars. This is one of the biggest challenges for the IFI today, according to Rosly (2005, pgs 347-349). Things get more complicated with the fact that these scholars have to look into more and more sophisticated contracts that are being developed by the industry. This is the main problem, according to Faisal Private Bank's CEO, Marco Rochat. Since there are “only a handful of scholars with the experience and reputation to judge the suitability of such a wide range of products”, the IFI faces a serious challenge in its quest for a share of the global financial market (Sa'Pinto, 2009).

Therefore, in order for the IFI to grow further and faster, there is a need for additional and well-qualified manpower that will be well-versed in and equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to carry on the mission and vision of the IFI pioneers. Everyone has to play a role, especially the governments of the Muslim countries and their respective institutions. A good example is the step taken by Bank Negara Malaysia (“BNM”) and its establishment of The International Centre for Education in Islamic Finance (“INCEIF”). However, more needs to be done in this regard and due attention should be given to the education of future leaders in Islamic finance by all the parties involved.

ii. Transparency, Regulation, and Supervision

As the latest financial crisis had been due to, among other things, a lack of proper regulatory policies, it is very important for the IFI to come up with a detailed framework for the regulation and supervision of the financial market. This is especially true with regard to the Islamic capital market. In order for Islamic banks to avoid taking on too much risk, there is a need for closer monitoring by the regulators (Sing).

The main role in the development of the regulatory framework should be taken up by various parties in the market; from governments to regulatory bodies, from financial institutions to *Shari'ah* scholars. As stated by Tag El Din and M Kabir Hassan, there is a need for *Shari'ah* scholars to continuously monitor and supervise the market so as to develop

“regulatory rules based on the realities in a given market” (2007, pg 251). Both regulation and supervision are “the most vital components of a sound operating framework for Islamic finance” (Ebrahim, 2004, pg 265). The institutions and regulatory bodies that are dealing with this issue include the Accounting and Auditing Organisation of Islamic Financial Institutions (or AAOIFI), the Islamic Financial Services Board (or IFSB), the International Islamic Rating Agency (or IIRA), and the International Islamic Financial Market (or IIFM).

There is no doubt that sound and viable regulations are needed for the IFI to not only develop further, but also to gain more credibility among the global masses. However, we should also make sure that the regulations leave enough space for the industry to breathe and function easily. A system that is too regulated is as bad as having no regulation at all.

To achieve better regulation and supervision, the transparency of the IFI is a must. Thus, the transparency of the IFI is crucial for the industry to continue its growth and to establish itself in the global financial market (Ebrahim, 2004, pgs 268-269). With this in mind, we believe that the transparency and disclosure of product structures should be mandatory upon Islamic financial institutions, to help them improve the quality of their products and also their validity. This disclosure and reporting by Islamic financial institutions should comply with the highest international standards and practices for financial and non-financial reporting. Furthermore, this disclosure of the relevant information should be done

accurately and in a timely manner (Khir, Gupta, & Shanmagam, 2008, pg 312).

iii. Standardisation and Harmonisation of Islamic Finance

Although there is a slight difference between standardisation and harmonisation, we will not focus on this difference but will use these 2 terms interchangeably for the sake of discussion. After all, the IFI lacks both standardisation and harmonisation; it is therefore suitable to use these 2 terms interchangeably.

The issue of lack of standardisation and/or harmonisation in Islamic finance has been pointed out time and again. Yet, it is still one of the IFI’s major concerns. Some argue that we do not need harmonisation/ standardisation and that the differences of opinions are the beauty of Islam, and as such they are not threats to the IFI. They say that the IFI has developed tremendously over the last couple of years, with over USD1 trillion of assets. This is a fact that cannot be disputed. However, the question to ask is: What would happen and how big would it have been if we had standardised it?

Others, however, acknowledge the different opinions but argue that for the IFI to prosper, we need standardised or harmonised rulings on basic products - to help the growth of Islamic banks and financial institutions. It is rightly pointed out that different opinions on similar issues, from different schools of thought, may create confusion among the general public as well as practitioners of Islamic finance (Khir, et al, 2008, pg 312).

Furthermore, the harmonisation of *Shari'ah* standards is a prerequisite for the successful development of the Islamic capital market in general, and Islamic money-market instruments in particular (Green, 2002). Thus, standardising the rules would make it easier for both companies and ordinary people to have a better understanding.

The operations of Islamic banks throughout the world differ to a great extent, and some sort of standardisation is urgently needed. Karina Robinson cited Nabeel Shoaib, global head of HSBC Amanah - the Islamic finance unit of global bank HSBC – as stating that "standardisation in Islamic finance is necessary to avoid fragmentation and to ultimately create a new asset class that can fully compete with conventional finance" (Robinson). Different opinions among *Shari'ah* scholars on what is and what is not *Shari'ah*-compliant hinders the development of the IFI. This lack of harmonisation – according to Marco Rochat – is due to the lack of a recognised body to oversee the IFI. The absence of standardisation or harmonisation in the international markets (especially between the Middle East and Malaysia) makes it hard to set up a global or even regional regulatory body.

Currently, there are different opinions and practices within a particular jurisdiction in a state or a region. Some products, for example *Bai' Bithaman Ajil* (or BBA), while being acceptable in Malaysia, are not acceptable in the Middle East and elsewhere. We believe that the standardisation of the practices and

rulings would also help them transcend borders more easily.

The harmonisation of global practices may promote the further growth and strength of the IFI. Although this task is partially tackled by some Islamic financial institutions such as AAOIFI and IFSB, it is far from completed. On this note, the recent introduction of "*Shari'ah* parameters" by Bank Negara Malaysia will help this cause. Having properly harmonised/ standardised products across the globe will benefit the industry as a whole, and will lead to economies of scale. Standardisation of common agreements would save time, effort and resources, giving practitioners of Islamic finance more room to focus on vital areas such as product development (Al-Jassar, 2002).

iv. Islamic Benchmark

There is no doubt that Islamic finance has unique characteristics that distinguish it from other systems. However, Islamic banks today operate in the shadow of the conventional financial system, and their practices are indirectly affected by certain changes in the conventional system (e.g. changes in interest rates).

Although interest is prohibited in Islam, interest rates do indeed affect Islamic finance and Islamic financial institutions, which commonly use the LIBOR as a benchmark; or, in the case of Malaysia, the KLIBOR, to determine their profit margins. Using interest rates is considered undesirable – according to Usmani (2002) – but it does not make the transaction invalid or *harām*, because the contract in itself does not contain interest.

However, he believes that this practice should be replaced with some kind of Islamic benchmark (pgs 48-49). The use of interest rates as a benchmark, although allowed by some *Shari'ah* scholars, should be avoided (Smolo, 2007; Vogel & Hayes, 1998, pg 139). There is thus a dire need for an Islamic benchmark that will enable Islamic financial institutions to price their products based on it, and to avoid any linkage to interest.

Responding to a question on whether we need to develop a unique Islamic benchmark, Rafe Haneef, Managing Director of Fajr Capital Plc in Kuala Lumpur, says that as long as the Islamic product fits within the mainstream product, there is no need to develop a unique Islamic benchmark.

"In my opinion, we cannot create another benchmark for an Islamic product that fits within the mainstream product (sukuk is like a bond) because the dominant benchmark (the conventional benchmark in this case) will force the new benchmark to converge. This is the "law of one price" in economics. However, if we change the way we structure our products (for example, if the redemption price of sukuk is based on the market price), then the pricing criteria would be different. We would have to look into the internal rate of return (or IRR) in that case. If we don't change the product, neither will the price," he concludes (MIF).

The citation above rightly points out that the mechanism and development of the Islamic products are crucial for the development of an Islamic benchmark. The author believes that there are, briefly,

2 steps in establishing an Islamic benchmark, as follows:

- i) There is a need to develop unique products based on the *Shari'ah* and to avoid the practice of "copy and paste". As long as our products are the same as or similar to conventional products, there will be no true distinction between them and they will therefore be governed by the same laws and rules of the game.
- ii) Without the implementation of the above, there will be no Islamic benchmark that is viable in the current financial environment. However, if we manage to develop true *Shari'ah*-based products, then we can simply collect the data from the market on a regular basis (e.g. daily or weekly), and come up with a benchmark that will be relevant only to the Islamic financial market.

Until and unless we review our practices, we will not be able to run on our own. Any attempt to develop an Islamic benchmark within the current system (bearing in mind that the IFI is currently a part of the conventional system) will lead to convergence, and will be subject to the law of one price, as mentioned by Rafe Haneef earlier.

Conclusion

The global financial crisis has shaken the international financial system; its repercussions are still being felt in the global markets. The IFI is not immune from this crisis; it has also been hit, although to a lesser extent. This fact alone shows that the IFI is indirectly linked to its conventional counterparty, as it lives under the same umbrella and is governed by the same rules of the game. In order for the IFI to free itself from these conventional chains, it needs to re-establish its position as a totally separate body within the global financial architecture. This can only be done if the current practices of the IFI are thoroughly reviewed, with the aim of reaching the true spirit of *Shari'ah* - without any shortcuts or legal tricks.

Right now, the IFI is a sub-set of the conventional financial system, which is governed by rules and regulations that may not be in line with the *Shari'ah*. By copying conventional mechanisms and applying the "*Shari'ah make-up*", we are not doing justice to Islamic finance. Rather, we are marking Islamic finance subordinate to the conventional financial system, thus making it less important.

In this paper, we have argued that without proper manpower that is knowledgeable and skilful, without some sort of standardisation/harmonisation, and without regulations, transparency and supervision, or a proper product structure that will lead to the development of an Islamic benchmark, the future of the IFI will be at stake. In this case, the IFI will slowly lose its vision and subsequently

converge with its conventional counterparty.

The IFI, with all these identified issues, cannot offer its full potential to the world now, when it desperately needs a sustainable and stable financial system after the international communities have been hit by the global crisis. However, this crisis has given the IFI a chance to review its existing practices and to come out of it more stable and much stronger than before.

Although the issues raised in this paper are not new, they are worth mentioning again as they still confront us. Lack of suitable and relevant data in support of the topic is nothing but proof of the arguments mentioned in this paper. Further research is needed to empirically show the importance of all these issues, for the sustainable growth of the IFI. The sooner we start dealing with these issues and stop putting them aside, the sooner we will be able to achieve the objectives of the *Shari'ah* (*maqāsid al- Shari'ah*) and the prosperity of the IFI. If the IFI fails to address these issues promptly, then it will not only negatively affect the future development of the industry, but will also lead to the convergence of the IFI with the dominant, conventional financial system.

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TOWARDS AN INFORMED MARKET GROWTH OF ISLAMIC FINANCIAL INDUSTRY

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